

AN INNOVATIVE CONCEPT OF DOUBLE DECKER STRADDLING BUS: OPTIMISED SOLUTION OF ROAD TRAFFIC & MASS TRANSPORTATION TO WORLD MEGACITIES

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ABSTRACT

As in current scenario worldwide is facing a buzz traffic problem so that also this paper presents a new concept of solving the problems of 21st century's megacities of the planet. Bangalore, Delhi, Mumbai. According to the Tom-tom Index reports, the traffic congestion within the city of Los Angeles in the United States of America topped the list for the second year in a row Chengdu, China, Recife, Brazil Salvador, Brazil Bucharest, Romania. Moscow, Russia, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, Istanbul, Turkey.

Dubai, Bangkok, Dhaka, Addis Ababa, Lagos and other great cities are getting chaotic by the day in spite of plethora of facilities. So for the solution of this problem we are going to introduce a double Decker Straddling bus as we all know straddling bus has made amazing progress in China. This bus used as the purpose of passenger travelling just like a metro train on road. This paper has give a concept of Double Decker straddling bus implementation form of Straddling bus in worldwide country for development purpose. Various available techniques and method, selection of sheet materials, engine power source capacity, equipment and their requirements, applications and other problems associated with straddling bus have been discussed in this paper. It also discussed the advantage avenue for future work which is needed to be carried out to put this technique to the next level of development.

Keywords: Elevated platform bus, Double Decker, Microcontroller, DC motor, RFID reader, RFID tag, LCD, IR sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, Buzzer, DC motor driver.

1. INTRODUCTION

If we start seeing long worm-like vehicle swallowing up cars on worldwide highways, don't be armed. Also electrical vehicle development is sustainability grow to minimized the pollution control as the same ways we are going to present the concept of Double Decker Straddling bus essentially oversized the trains that have been hollowed out to allow the cars through – sort of like mobile tunnel. Approximately 1800 people can board the bus, removing the need for additional subway system is pollution-prone cars. The company behind the buses estimates each one will cut fuel composition by 1000 tons and carbon emission by 2500 tons, city lab reports

China don't yet have the extreme driving culture America does. The proposed Double Decker straddling bus would be all electric controlled, travel approximately 40-50 kmph, and give seven feet of subway to cars traveling underneath. If the test actually happens it'll be first time Double Decker straddling bus become more than first through experiments. The idea was first proposed way back in 1969, and Song revived the plans in 2010 but intimately well in China and our concept is going to introduce four trailer double Decker straddling bus which are optimized solution of road traffic and mass transportation also minimized the fuel consumption which are best solution of ecofriendly solution of worldwide.

INNOVATIVE CONCEPT:

At our Current trends there are four main models on public transportation e.i. subway, light rail, bus rapid transit (BRT), and the normal bus. The proposed system is Double Decker straddling bus and it eliminates the need of driver, thus any human error is ruled out, in this project microcontroller from ARM family has been used of CPU, whenever the train arrives at the station it stops automatically as sensed by an IR sensor, then the converger starts automatically so that the passengers can go inside and outside the bus. The movement of the bus is controlled by a motor driver IC interfaced to the microcontroller. The train incorporates a buzzer to alert the passengers before staring, as the bust destination the process repeats thus achieving the desired operation. The advantage of double Decker straddling bus over straddling bus is that for double public mass transportation hence reduce the traffic as well as transportation system.

Since the bus is no higher than a tractor – trailer, roadway over passes will usually not be a problem, the bus world run along a fixed route, edge of the two lanes it straddles and the overall height 5 to 8.5m (20ft. in to 24 ft.) The passengers onboard the bus are exacted to experience a ride comparable to riding in the upper level of a double Decker bus. They will board and alight at station at the side of the rode with platforms at the bus from a station similar to a pedestrian over pass. The bus will be electrically power using over head line or other root electrical contact system designed for it, supplemented with photo voltaic panels, batteries, or supper capacitors on board.

Block Diagram of Innovative Concept of Double Decker Straddling Bus-

Fig. (Front view of Double Decker Straddling Bus)

Further the project can be enhanced by making this system more advanced by displaying the status of the bus over an LCD screen for the convenience of the passengers in this REID based. Automatic face collecting system using RFID card, ticketing explained that a system that used the station based location information. Card is sensed twice while entering the bus and while leaving the bus.

Fig. Side view to Double Decker straddling bus

Silent Features:

1. This is a new concept of Mass transportation and Road Traffic which will fully optimized by the concept of Double Decker straddling bus.
2. In this concept in ground floor is passes of a path through which vehicle is pass away like a car two wheelers. If a heavy vehicle is in front there is also a facility to sense by a senser which are also include inside the ground floor of bus then the bus will self lift as per height of vehicle which are going to pass away by the vehicle. Self lifting mechanism is on basis of self operated hydraulic lift with balancing condition of Double Decker Straddling bus.
3. This concept is based on (Three) 3- Trailer vehicles in which first floor a large number of passenger's seats are also available approx. 200 and some reserve seat facilities too. After that in second floor 150 seating arrangement is also provided to provide the luxuries facilities to Indian culture and just like Boeing 727planes.
4. A Road track is to decide the desired path of bus to which can move and follow the path.
5. This bus can opt by each categories of person as per demand of public.
6. **This bus is balanced on each phase due to 3- trailer system:-**

Scenario 1: (When Double Decker straddling Bus is on level ground/almost level ground and static)

Scenario 2: (When Double Decker straddling Bus is moving in forward direction on level ground/almost level ground.

Scenario 3: (When Double Decker straddling Bus is moving in reverse direction on level ground/almost level ground).

Scenario 4: (When Double Decker straddling Bus is moving in forward direction on an ascending incline like flyover etc.)

Scenario 5 (When Double Decker straddling Bus is moving in forward direction on a descending incline like flyover etc.)

Scenario 6 (When Double Decker straddling Bus is moving in reverse direction on an ascending incline like flyover etc.)

Scenario 7 (When Double Decker straddling Bus is moving in reverse direction on a descending incline like flyover etc.)

Flowchart of Double Decker Straddling Bus

Flowchart of Double Decker Straddling Bus-

The bus would have alarms to warn cars traveling too close to it, and signals to warn other vehicles when it is about to turn. It would have inflatable evacuation slides like those of an aircraft. Optional features could include sensors to keep it from colliding with a person or object such as an over-height vehicle from going underneath, repeater traffic signals underneath up ahead, and animated light displays to simulate stationary objects to prevent disorientation of drivers underneath.

Proposed and actual trials –

At the time of the 2016 unveiling of the scale model, it was reported that a prototype would be deployed by mid-2016. It contracts with his company for pilot projects involving the construction of hundreds of kilometres of tracks beginning in 2016. In China there are four main modes of public transportation:

Subway, light rail, bus rapid transit (BRT) and normal buses. The express coach would be a substitute for BRT and augment its advantages. To modify the road for the bus, two options are available: rails can be laid on the edges of the lanes that the bus occupies, or two white

lines can be painted on the road to facilitate use of autopilot technology. Rails would offer less wheel rolling resistance and better energy efficiency. For either option, it may be necessary to widen the lanes occupied by the bus to accommodate the bus wheels and undercarriage whilst allowing other vehicles to pass under the bus two abreast. Since the bus is no higher than a tractor trailer, Roadway overpasses will usually not be a problem.

Criticism and controversies

Critics of the project when the concept was unveiled in 2010 have questioned whether the hovering bus could interact safely with other vehicles, particularly when drivers maneuver to change lanes. Critics had also argued that the tracks would require relatively straight roads not found in many older urban areas, and that the overhead boarding stations that the bus needed would take up too much space.[3][4] According to Song Youzhou, the project's chief engineer, guardrails would be constructed between the bus tracks and the car lanes that pass through the elevated bus to prevent traffic accidents.

Conclusion

This system is mainly to support the public transportation system. It highly reduces the modern day problem of traffic jams that we are facing today. It will carry the large number of people which will lessen the load on public transport, more energy efficient and optimize passenger service automatically in real time. In terms of operational efficiency and cost-saving, driverless networks avoiding human error. Due to its low cost and low settling time it can be implemented in short duration.

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Reference

- 3D Express Coach to be put into trial in Beijing CNTV.news, August 25, 2010
- The Straddling Bus. August 7, 2013. Retrieved April 14, 2015. 3
- Prakash Ratan , Chandra Jogi - Auto Metro Train to Shuttle Between Stations - International Journal & Magazine of Engineering, Technology, Management and Research , Volume No: 2 (2015), Issue No: 5 (May).
- R.Valarmathi, G.Karthika -Smart Ticketing System in Metro Rail - International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering , Vol. 3, Special Issue 3, April 2014
- Thabit Sultan Mohammed1, Wiisam Fahmii All-- Azzo 2,, Mohammed Ahmed Akaak3, Mohammed Laheeb Suroor4 Full Automation in Driverless Trains: A Microcontroller-Based Prototype - International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering Vol. 3, Issue 7, July 2014
- Limer, Eric (August 3, 2016). "Chinese Straddling bus can carry 300 people". Yahoo Tech. Retrieved 4 August 2016. 15. Bosker, Bianca (3 August 2010).
- "China Plans Huge Buses That Can DRIVE OVER Cars (PHOTOS)". Huffington Post. Retrieved 22 June 2013. 16.
- "China's elevated bus: Futuristic 'straddling bus' hits the road". BBC News. 2016-08-03. Retrieved 2016-08-03. 17.
- "Straddling Bus Begins Road Tests". Seeker. 2016-08-03. Retrieved 2016-08-04